

TRAINING ATHLETES IN MORAL AND VOLITIONAL AND SPIRITUAL QUALITIES

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Abstract: *In the moral education of young athletes, a directly important role is played by sports activities, which provide a conscious discipline, great opportunities for the upbringing of comrades, teamwork, patriotism, hard work and other positive emotions. Children and adolescents under the role of motivating and guiding the coach in the moral education of young men and girls, the sports team is especially important.*

The high prestige and respect of the educator gives the opportunity to successfully apply such an effective method of forming moral consciousness as the method of persuasion in educational work. The coach, who has earned the respect of his students, achieves that all his instructions are easily fulfilled.

INTRODUCTION

In the formation of the social behavior of young athletes, sports play an important role in gaining social experience. The sports team compels the school students to have a certain social burden. The position of the young athlete on the team, his sports results, behavior are evaluated by the coach and peers. According to the age and interests of schoolchildren, there is a desire to integrate into small groups. One of the forms of prospects for the unification of adolescents into such groups was sports training. The sports team of children and adolescents attracts a teenager as a form of small groups. For this reason, the social work carried out by young athletes in the team as a member of a circle of young athletes, a team guide is of great importance. It is necessary to stimulate the social initiative of young athletes, to educate them to realize that the interests of the team, the group are their interests and must be followed.

The correct choice of methods of moral education, their timely systematic and comprehensive use largely determines the success of educational work. Based on the content and conditions of Organization of various forms of work on physical education, it is necessary to take students from their initial simple visions of the norms and rules of cultural ethics to a complete, deep understanding and compliance with them in sports training and everyday life. It is worth noting that in the practice of work activities of some coaches there are cases of insufficient assessment of moral education. This is reflected in a one-sided approach to the training process, in which the coach focuses on the issues of technical and sports training, harming the educational work with young athletes.

MAIN PART

Spiritual-will training. Spiritual - will training of an athlete is a process of moral education, will Training, which, in its pedagogical essence, is carried out in accordance with the conditions of sports activities. The tasks solved in the process of spiritual and will training of an athlete are to improve moral qualities in sports activities. Feelings of patriotism, protection of team pride, spreading the fame of the motherland to the world, improving human qualities, improving the qualities of being able to widely use all opportunities on the path of victory form the basis of spiritual will preparation. At the same time, in the preparation of spiritual will, the character of athletes is formed.

A gallant, often even invulnerable type of activity that requires a full manifestation of the qualities of an athlete's will. The cultivation of strong will, striving for a goal, initiative, demanding, determination and qualities of courage, endurance and self-control remain an integral part of the preparation of spiritual will. In all sports, moral qualities and spiritual preparation should be the same. Because in each athlete requires Will training from athletes to different degrees. The manifestation of will qualities depends on the concrete conditions of sports processes and carries out the manifestation of various aspects of will. With this, general and special will preparation are distinguished from each other.

One of the most important of the special tasks performed in the process of Will preparation is to purposefully formulate the instructions that are given directly for the competition, overcome the negative emojis that appear during the competitions and ensure the ability to control the psychic state of athletes. In sports, the preparation of spiritual Will is organized according to the general principles of moral education, using the motor methods of moral education.

The importance of the Sport is also considered important. He will be the main factor in the upbringing of Will and character in the athlete. Compliance with a strict agenda, withstanding heavy physical loads, overcoming negative emotions, dealing with internal and external difficulties in the process of training and competitions will be a factor in educating the athlete in volitional qualities and forming a sports character. Conditions in sports activities also provide great opportunities for the education of conscious discipline, friendship, community, patriotism, hard work and other moral feelings and qualities.

Moral and volitional training of an athlete is a process of moral and volitional education, which is carried out according to its pedagogical Moxies, depending on its application in the context of sports activities. Sport is a laborious and complex activity that requires strong will. The upbringing of the qualities of strong will, striving for a goal, initiative and perseverance forms an integral part of the training of an athlete.

In the process of training an athlete, it is necessary to develop the following qualities:

- loyalty to the National idea, striving to put social and state work above his personal work, regular care about his health in labor and patriotism;

- participation in practical activities of the public, improving sports skills, feeling responsible in front of them for their behavior in living conditions, not allowing a careless look at work.

The high moral qualities of athletes are formed in labor, in various activities, behavior, in the treatment of people and serve as a resource in determining sports ethics. Sports ethics it is the sum of the norms and rules of behavior that are mandatory for an athlete in specific activities (training, competition, visual performances).

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

These requirements contribute to the upbringing of sports hard work in our athletes in the struggle for high-conscious discipline, physical maturity, strengthening health and creative longevity. Athletes must love their homeland and sport through their collective and active struggle in setting high sports achievements and World Records, keep the sports flag high internationally, teach young people their sports experience. In addition, sports ethics requires the manifestation of universal qualities: humility, truthfulness, truthfulness, pure language, politeness, respect for the opponent, respect for the audience and non-indulgence in manliness.

The norms of ethics implemented in sports training remain inherent in the character of a person. The specific personality of the athlete, the variety of means used, forms of training, external environment and training conditions — all this allows it to affect the consciousness, emotion, willpower and behavior of those involved in all aspects. It is especially important to moral education in the activity of the movement. For example, in gymnastics, movement activity requires strict consistency. This forces the athlete to control himself, and restrain his emotions; it requires courage, boldness, courage and pleasure when practicing at height. In the upbringing of moral qualities, the game is of particular importance, it requires self-sacrifice, the ability to control one's own emotions in the context of confrontation, being active, providing mutual assistance, Brotherhood, striving for a single goal. They put the athlete's struggle in a certain strict setting, require pure discipline, educate truthfulness, pure diligence and a solid character.

Theoretical preparation. There is such a wide range of knowledge necessary for an athlete that they do not fall into any of the preparatory parts. Physical education includes knowledge of the history of sports, weightlifting, Sports Physiology, hygiene, medical supervision in sports, theoretical foundations of weightlifting. Mastering this knowledge forms part of theoretical training. Along with the progress of sports, the role of theoretical preparedness also develops. A deep understanding of the mechanisms of weightlifting, the functioning of the organism's life and the factors of progress the high level of intellectual culture serves as the main tool and factor of sports achievements. In addition to the fact that theoretical training harmoniously develops the personality in every possible way, it also organizes conscious and successful engagement with sports gadgets.

The theoretical training of an athlete is carried out mainly in forms characteristic of mental education and independent reading. Theoretical training will be directly in sports

training as an outline of practical training in combination with technical, tactical, spiritual Will and physical training. The processes of general and special training of the athlete are multi-faceted and have their own characteristics. They will be in harmony.

Physical training provides the basis and conditions for solving technical and tactical training tasks. At the same time, the results of technical and tactical training assess the level of physical fitness. Spiritual Will preparation forms athletes' attitude to sports, training and competitions. Theoretical training, on the other hand, allows you to analyze modern styles of playing sports.

Pedagogical methods of upbringing. In moral volitional upbringing, it is necessary to use various methods: in the form of an explanation, through persuasion, conversation and other verbal influence, instructive examples, practical teaching are used. Using the method of persuasion through verbal influence, the trainer explains the principles of morality, code, the requirements of sports ethics, makes sure to be volitional, teaches to look at the collective, objectively at their own results and behavior. Along with the explanation, encouragement, praise, hypocrisy, etc. are used.

The desire of an athlete to self-discipline is evidenced by the fact that the athlete has maturity, confidence, willpower and character. Personal upbringing consists of: 1) self-control, ability to distinguish between positive and negative, critical assessment of one's own behavior, listening to the opinion of others about oneself; 2) analysis of one's own activities and behavior. Personal upbringing helps to motivate oneself, to make a commitment to oneself. Self-overcoming makes sure of its capabilities. Self-education will depend on personal characteristics, culture, experience, etc.

CONCLUSION

Success in sports is not about improving the physical abilities inherent in this sport, but about requires the development of all physical qualities. Special physical exercises play a key role in this. Tempering treatments and hygienic conditions are widely used in the process of training sessions. The importance of these factors and rules in sports activities changes in accordance with the fact that training processes become more complex and physical loads increase. Physical fitness is the foundation of the content of sports training.

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